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ACTIVITIES RELATED TO APOIDEA POLLINATORS
IN THE FORESTE CASENTINESI, MOUNT FALTERONA
AND CAMPIGNA NATIONAL PARK, DURING 2021

Attività legate agli impollinatori Apoidei realizzate nel Parco Nazionale delle Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona e Campigna, nel corso del 2021

The rising threats that pollinating insects are facing, prompted the Italian Ministry of the Environment to direct funding from the “Biodiversity Directive” towards the safeguard of pollinators. Since 2019, all National Parks in the Apennines have started a collaboration with several academic and research partners to provide protocols for the monitoring and the study of pollinating insects (UNIVERSITY OF PISA 2020a, 2020b; CREA 2020; UNIVERSITY OF ROMA “TOR VERGATA” 2019; POTTS *et al.*, 2021).

This study was focused on Apoidea group of Hymenoptera and research activities started in 2021, workplan was organized into three sections.

The first one is about *Apis mellifera* populations. Relying on the National beekeeping registry, it was possible to establish that beekeeping exerts a limited pressure on Foreste Casentinesi National Park’s environment. Only 34 beekeepers are active, with a total of 59 apiaries in about 36.800 hectares, with a prevalence of nomadic breeding form linked to the production of chestnut honey and fir honeydew. Apiaries tend to be concentrated in few areas characterized by a specific composition of tree species (in only 3 of 11 municipalities we find 47 apiaries of the total 59). This implies that only a small number of municipalities are characterized by high beekeeping pressure in some areas, and only during the summer period. In the remainder of the year, beekeeping pressure is zeroed. In addition, contacts were made with some volunteer beekeepers, who provided samples of spring and summer wax and honey. The analyses carried out on honey sam-

ples at Tor Vergata University of Rome showed total absence of drug residues, while metals were found to be present only in some samples and in very low quantities. The situation is different for waxes, which have more conspicuous residues of heavy metals, the origin of which is still not entirely clear. Finally, each beekeeper provided bee samples, which are currently under study to determine the local subspecies of *Apis mellifera* and the possible presence of local ecotypes. A bee sample from a wild swarm was also included.

The second activity provides the creation of habitat spots, in which a control unit is positioned. Each unit consists of a bulletin board containing nests for Apoidea supplied by the University of Pisa. Units were placed so that at least one apiary was present near the habitat. In this way, three times a year it is possible to collect pollen samples from wild bees in flight and from managed honeybees. At the end of the year, one of the nests was then taken and pollen contained in the brood cells was collected. The analyses carried out by University of Pisa highlighted for managed honeybees an almost exclusive propensity to *Hedera* pollen during early (June-July) and late (August-September) summer. Whereas, the diet of wild bees seemed almost exclusively linked to the other species of plants bloomed during the sampling periods. Furthermore, it should be considered that in the National Park the possibility of trophic interaction between wild and managed honeybees are almost exclusively limited to the summer, according to the breeding methods present in the area. And also in this period, it seems that there is a trophic partition between wild and managed honey bees. Wild bee samples were also determined by CREA in Bologna.

The third activity focused on the study of wild bee populations. Given that the National Park did not have previous data, it was decided to proceed for the first two years with survey activities, useful to identify the largest possible number of species. The samples were then determined by CREA in Bologna. Three transects were created: one at high altitude (1653 m) and one at low altitude (769 m) and a third was added at an intermediate altitude. In 2021, the transects were covered once a month from March to October. A total of 139 Apoidea were sampled in the transects and 17 in the habitat spots for 156 total sample, of which 123 has already been identified at a specific level. It was possible to identify specimens of all 6 families of Apoidea present in Italy (Melittidae, Apidae, Megachilidae, Halictidae, Colletidae and Andrenidae), for a total of 61 species divided into 22 genera (respectively 62 and 23 if we count *Apis mellifera*).

These activities will be performed throughout 2022. Subsequently it will be evaluated whether to maintain current research activities or to modify current approaches (ie. replacing survey with a monitoring scheme).

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